

The impact of Single Motherhood: A Sociological Analysis

Mohamed Salihu. M., *Assistant Professor in Sociology, School of Law, Sathyabama Institute of Science and Technology (Deemed to be University), Chennai- 600119.*

Abstract: “A single mother is a mother who has a dependent child or dependent children and who is widowed, separated, divorced, or unmarried. As a single mother she has sacrificed her social and financial independence”- Collins English Dictionary. In a universal stance, data from 89 countries shows that out of all the lone-parent households, single mothers head over 84 percent of them, translating to 101.3 million. According to the '*Progress of the World's Women 2019-2020*' report by United Nations Women, an estimated 4.5 percent of all Indian households (13 million) are run by single mothers. The poverty rate of single-mother residences in India, at 38 percent, is still conspicuously higher in comparison 22.6 percent for the dual-parent residences in the country. This research focuses on the challenges and issues of single mothers like financial obstruction, emotional consequences of growing up in a single mother household may include feelings of sadness, abandonment, difficulty socializing and loneliness, increased frustration and an increased danger of violent behavior. In this study the researcher used qualitative research method and purposive sampling technique to collect the data from the respondents. This study applies Structural-functional and symbolic interaction approach to study the social consequences of single motherhood. Results showed that single mothers are more likely to accounts higher level of chronic stress, lack of financial resource and episodes of depression.

Keywords: Single mother, Social Consequences, Children from Single mother family, Structural-functional perspective and symbolic interaction perspective.

INTRODUCTION

According to Dowd Nancy (1997), a single parent is a parent, not living with spouse or partner, who has most of the day-to-day responsibilities in raising the child or children. In a universal stance, data from 89 countries shows that out of all the lone-parent households, single mothers head over 84 percent of them, translating to 101.3 million. According to the '*Progress of the World's Women 2019-2020*' report by United Nations Women, an estimated 4.5 percent of all Indian households (13 million) are run by single mothers. The poverty rate of single-mother residences in India, at 38 percent, is still conspicuously higher in comparison 22.6 percent for the dual-parent residences in the country. In India, raising of children in joint family pattern has changed a lot, with the advent of industrialization and globalization. Family lives have been interrupted with the hasty social change that comes with the globalization. Today, many of the old customs and traditions that have been taught and followed for many years are becoming obsolete. What was unacceptable in the olden days is now becoming fast and rapidly rising trend. Because of single motherhood dependent children are affecting in the day to day life. Dependent children are defined as either being below the age of 18 or up to 24 if economically inactive. This research focuses on the challenges and issues of single motherhood like financial obstruction, emotional consequences of growing up in a single mother household may include feelings of sadness, abandonment, difficulty socializing and loneliness, increased frustration and an increased danger of violent behaviour.

Socialization

The socialization of children is very important for the continuity of any culture. The family is said to be the most important agent of socialization, especially for children. Children in most communities are raised in a highly structured and disciplined manner, parents helped to instill and inculcate strong basic moral, spiritual, social, physical and cognitive principles in their children (Santrock, 2002). Socialization plays vital role to teach discipline to the children. When single mother leads the family, it is very difficult to socialize her child because of her day to day commitments. Sociologist George Herbert Mead believed that people develop self-images through interactions with other people. He argued that the self, which is the part of a person's

personality consisting of self-awareness and self-image, is a product of social experience. Both father and mother teach their children about self-respect, self-image and awareness. Absence of father in the family affects the social experience.

THEORETICAL FRAME WORK

Functionalists view the family unit as a construct that fulfills important functions and keeps society running smoothly. Explain the social functions of the family through the perspective of structural functionalism functionalists identify a number of functions families typically perform: reproduction; socialization; care, protection, and emotional support; assignment of status; and regulation of sexual behavior through social norms. For functionalists, the family creates well-integrated members of society by instilling the social culture into children. Father plays an important role in the family to socialize the children rather than mother.

Symbolic Interactionism is a theory that analyzes patterns of communication, interpretation, and adjustment between individuals in society. The theory is a framework for understanding how individuals interact with each other and within society through the meanings of symbols. Single mothers are have interaction with their children very rarely and absence of father in the home affect the children's role-taking which is a key mechanism that permits an individual to appreciate another person's perspective and to understand what an action might mean to that person. Role-taking emerges at an early age through activities such as playing house. Symbolic interactionists explore the changing meanings attached to family. Symbolic interactionists argue that shared activities help to build emotional bonds and that marriage and family relationships are based on negotiated meanings.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The role of single motherhood is challenging one especially when the family is headed by a women. Problem of single mother are linked with the upbringing of children, their future and setting down in life. Till the time children get married and or get jobs they are dependent on the single mother. After that the problems are considerably reduced. The present study focuses on their social, economic and emotional problems of managing the house, problems related to their children. The number of single mothers has grown phenomenally all across the world in the last three decades.

The research intends to find out the following objectives:

- To examine the prevalence of problems faced by children in single parent homes
- To find out if boys other than girls appear to have significantly greater incidence of problems in single parent homes.
- To study the social and mental well-being of single parent.
- To suggest solutions to such problems.

The research design for this study is a qualitative research method. This method used to analyse the social consequences of single motherhood. The sampling technique for this study is Purposive Sampling which is Non probability Sampling Techniques that a researcher uses to choose a sample of respondent from a population. It is widely used in qualitative research for the identification and selection of information-rich cases related to the phenomenon of interest. The sample is restricted to single mother families aged 19 to 59. Based on the data saturation final sample counts 11 single mothers and 11 children in Chennai, Tamilnadu. The study was undertaken in two areas of Chennai namely Kotturpuram and Adyar. It is very difficult to have a list of single mothers and their children in the study area to conduct purposive sampling. However the researcher got the single-mothers contact details from the first respondent who is working in a self help group. The study population for the research constitutes children of single parents who are above the age of 10 years and their single mothers. The criterion of 10 years is purposefully selected to make sure children have meaningful experience (for instance interacting with peers in schools) and are realistically be able to describe their experience. However, it should be noted that this might have its own limitations on the study in a sense that the experience of children below 10 years are not included in the study.

The focus of data collection is on critical and insightful description of the challenges from children's own perspective and how they make of their experience and why they think their parent's marital status has affected their life. 11 children were interviewed based on the principle of data saturation. Accordingly, the study participants for this study were two groups: Children and their single parents. Data were collected from children aged above ten years old. Through in-depth interview children themselves are asked to describe and narrate their life experience of being a child of single mother parents. The focus of data collection is on critical and insightful description of the challenges from children's own perspective and how they make of their

experience and why they think their parent's marital status has affected their life. 11 children were interviewed based on the principle of data saturation. Further information on children's experience was collected from a parent's perspective. Data collection from parents was focused on how their single status is impacting their children's life and how do they try to deal with any of these changes. Tool of data collection for this study is in-depth interview method. It is wholly open ended instrument in which interviewers have a list of topics they want respondents to talk about but are free to phrase the questions as they wish. The respondents are free to answer in any way they choose.

DATA ANALYSIS

Information about Single mother

Single mother A is a 30 years old single mother, of a daughter separated from her husband because "she caught her husband cheating and lying" She is originally from Trichy, but moved to Adyar before five years.

Single mother B is a 37 years a widowed from Madurai currently residing in Kotturpuram with her 13 years old son and 10 years old daughter. Her husband died before seven years. She expressed that she was so distressed after the death of her husband and migrated to Kotturpuram. She Manage the family by selling handloom products.

Single mother C is a 35 years old widowed mother and living with her 14 year old son. She is daily laborer and lives in shelter.

Single mother D is a 29 years old sole mother with four children. She is widowed and supports the whole family by selling water can. She has serious health problem and because of that she is frightened and distressed about her children future. She believes she has no good relationship with the surrounding community.

Single mother E is a 38 years old and mother of 15 year old son. She is daily laborer. Her husband died before 10 years. She said that she committed herself for her son and she doesn't want to get married because she is "afraid that only child might get abused by my partner"

Single mother F is 40 years old and living with her two children in Adyar. She says she is separated from her husband due to his drinking behavior. She has attended her education until grade three. She is living in a rented house from private owners. She manages the family by selling lemons, and potatoes in the area.

Single mother G has three children. She is a 35 years old and support the family by washing other people's clothes. She did not have a chance to get enrolled in school and she cannot write nor read. She said that the difficult thing in life is being both a mother and a father.

Single mother H is a 30 years old single mother with her a 10 year old daughter and 3 year old son. She attended education till grade seven. The family lives in a private rented house.

Single mother I is a 40 years old sole mother living in Adyar with her 16 years old daughter and 9 years old son. She is daily laborer and living in a private rented home. The family has serious economic problem and due to this the mother cannot afford to pay for housing.

Single mother J is a 45 years old sole mother with four children aged 9, 11, 14 and 16. She got divorced from her husband due to his drinking behavior. He was irresponsible for the family. She wasn't gone to school in her entire life. The families are living in cardboard made house. J says children work after they return from school and support her.

Single mother K is a 40 years old single mother with a 13 years old daughter. Her husband died two years ago after a long period of time of sickness. She is illiterate and she supports her family being a daily laborer. She over controlled her daughter due to fear of losing her because of bad behavior.

Information about Children

The researcher supplemented the data from single mothers with data from children. A total of eleven children were interviewed. This section presents a summary of the basic information about the children.

Child A is the oldest daughter of a single mother experienced a loose of her father when she was 11 years old child. She is 15 years old and has 3 younger brothers. She experienced financial difficulties after the death of her father because, her mother does not have permanent job.

Child B is 12 years daughter of a single mother grew up without the father, since her parent's separation. As per to the story she heard from her mother the reason why they got separated was the due to her father's drinking behavior. Due to the financial problem in the family participant B is working as a daily laborer in mechanic shop after school and in weekends.

Child C is 16 years old daughter of single mother families living with her younger brother and destitute mother in Kotturpuram. She is grade 8 student in a governmental school.

Child D is 13 years old daughter of a single mother experiencing losses of father when she was a baby. She does not have an experience of having a father. She is attending her education in governmental school.

Child E is 11 years only daughter and child of a single mother experienced lose of her father due to death 4 years ago. She is attending grade 4 class in governmental school. The child's mother is daily labor and her income is not enough to cover their expense.

Child F is 13 years only son and child of a single mother experienced parent's separation since he was 3 years old. The mother did not explain to him why they get separated. He is attending his grade 6 education in governmental school. After school time, he also works with his mother.

Child G is 14 year oldest son of a single mother. The child's parents were separated when he was a small baby. The father does not support the family; the only source of income is his mother. He has a younger sister.

Child H is 15 years oldest son of a single mother experiencing lose of his father due to death 4 years ago. Because, mostly his mother is working in night and weekends and sometimes stayed for two- three days, H is responsible for taking care of his younger sister and for himself too. He is grade 6 student in a governmental school.

Child I is 14 years old boy living with his single mother. His mother supports the family by selling vegetables in the evening.

Child J is 14 years old son of a single mother grew up without the father due to his father's death. He does not have an experience of having and living with a father. He told me that because his mother is illiterate, she does not support him in doing his home works.

Child K is 15 years old daughter of a single mother experienced losing of a father due to death. She is grade 8 student in governmental school and living with her single mother and a younger brother. She said that, because my mother has financial difficulties I do not dare to ask her to buy me things I want. She supports her mother in doing household chores after school.

FINDINGS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Measuring by their monthly income, educational attainment, and occupation, socioeconomic backgrounds of the single-mothers and children correspondingly fell on lower socioeconomic status. A majority of single-mothers held at least a primary education and the rest four are illiterate. All single mothers are having not permanent job, they are daily laborers. Majority of single mother and children have not get support from their relatives and kin. From the interview, almost all children have good relationship with their single mothers. Due to their mothers educational status and lack of enough time to spend together, all children does not have support in doing their homework from their mothers.

Much of the current research on single-motherhood family in the West is a result of the increasing awareness of the growing number of families maintained by single-mother. This concern is partly rooted in the Freudian theory that emphasized the significant role of both mother and father in shaping the child's personality (Freud, 1905/62), and partly in theories, that regarded the father to be the only appropriate sex-role model for sons (Bandura and Walters, 1963) and an important link between the family and society (Parsons and Bales, 1955).

The absence of the father and consequently living in mother headed homes, is found to be negatively related to such major development areas as sex-role development, cognitive functioning, and personal and social adjustment. (Biller, 1981; Blechman, 1982; Radin, 1981; and Shinn,1978). Boys from fatherless homes are found to be less masculine (Biller, 1974; Blanchard and Biller, 1971; Hetherington,1966) and girls show difficulty in interacting with males (Hetherington, 1972). The effect is found to be less harmful for girls than for boys (Hetherington, Cox and Cox,1978; Santrock,1972). Father absence is reported to have a negative impact on cognitive and intellectual functioning resulting in poor school performance, especially among boys (Blanchard and Biller,1971). Paternal deprivation is frequently found to be associated with juvenile delinquency (Bacon, Child and Barry, 1963), anxiety, and low self esteem (Biller,1981). Studies indicated that single mothers experience usually high level of

psychological distress because they are exposed to more stressful events and more ongoing strain in the form of low income than households headed by Married couples (McLanahan, 1984, p.1; see also Harbest, 2012).

Findings of Sigle-Rushton and McLanahan (2004) that carried out a similar study concerning the well being of the child in the absence of one parent. The outcome of the study draws our attention to the fact that children raised by one biological parent fare worse on a host of social and economic measures than children raised by both biological parents. Many of single parent households earn low income and are disproportionately living in poverty. Single parents, usually mothers, are in a lack of financial support from a father often and are often required to work longer hours there by making children receive less attention and guidance which impede their social development as well as education performance (Kunz, 2014)

The results of the study revealed that financial problem was the main stressor for majority of the single mothers and this study further reveals that Boys in single parent families face greater problems than girls in single mother families. Also, the severity of problems faced by children in single parent homes depends on the age of the child at time of parental separation. The emotional life of the single mother was also affected by their single status. Majority of the single mother reported that they felt lonely, helpless, hopeless, lack of identity and lack of confidence. In social sphere majority of single mothers tried to avoid attending social gatherings and had changed their dressing style due to depression they had develop poor food and eating habits. Majority of the single mothers found it hard to maintain discipline among the children due to absence of male members. The mothers complained about loneliness, traumatic and depression and found it difficult to handle the responsibility of childcare and to establish a routine for her children. Government of India should collect and publish data on number of single mothers in India. It is responsibility of Ministry of Women and Child Development to assess the status of single mothers in India. Unfortunately Ministry of Women and Child Development and National Commission for Women are silent on this vital issue. Even National Sample Survey Office and NITI Aayog have not conducted any study on this aspect. Single mothers are living in very pathetic condition with social, economic, cultural and psychological problems.

The government may initiate educative and enlightenment program on how to improve and sustain two parents family through the radio, television and other mass media. Marital disunity is

a major cause of single parenting. Therefore, to avoid this, parents should tolerate, accommodate, appreciate and understand each other in marriage. Forces of disunity should be ignored, de-emphasized, if not eliminated. Both parents should try to stay together for the sake of good upbringing of their children. Whenever there is problem in the home, the couple should try and see the counsellor for a help or otherwise, settle the problems within themselves amicably. There is the need for the recognition of individual differences in students and the need to deal with them accordingly. Counselors should provide the necessary assistance and psychological support for students from single parent family so as to overcome their emotional problems Policy makers should always take the subjective views of their wards into consideration in order to avert the problem of single parenthood in the society.

REFERENCE

- ❖ Bales, R. F., & Parsons, T. (2014). *Family: Socialization and interaction process*. routledge.192.
- ❖ Bandura, A., & Walters, R. H. (1963). Social learning and personality development. 89.
- ❖ Biller, H. B. (1981). Father absence, divorce, and personality development. *The role of the father in child development*, 2, 499..
- ❖ Blechman, E. A. (1982). Are children with one parent at psychological risk? A methodological review. *Journal of Marriage and the Family*, 182.
- ❖ Dowd, N. E. (1999). *In defense of single-parent families*. NYU Press.101.
- ❖ Freud, S. (1962). Three essays on the theory of sexuality (J. Strachey, Trans.). *New York*.94.
- ❖ Hetherington, E. M. (1966). Effects of paternal absence on sex-typed behaviors in Negro and white preadolescent males. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 4(1), 87.
- ❖ Hetherington, E. M. (1972). Effects of father absence on personality development in adolescent daughters. *Developmental Psychology*, 7(3), 313.
- ❖ Kunz, M. (2014). The effects of a single parent home on a child's behavior. Available at <http://www.livestrong.com/article/83670-effects-single-parent-home-childs/>(Accessed June 2020).
- ❖ McLanahan, S. S., & Sorensen, A. B. (1984). Life events and psychological well-being: A reexamination of theoretical and methodological issues. *Social Science Research*, 13(2), 120.
- ❖ Radin, N. (1981). The role of the father in cognitive, academic, and intellectual development. *The role of the father in child development*, 2, 380.

- ❖ Santrock, J.W. (2004) “Life- Span Development” (9th ed.) McGraw-Hill Companies, Inc. New York.120.
- ❖ Shinn, M. (1978). Father absence and children's cognitive development. *Psychological Bulletin*, 85(2), 295.